

COMPARISON OF WOODCARVING AND PAPER FOLDING APPROACH ON PRE-SERVICE BIOLOGY TEACHERS' ABILITY TO DEVELOP PHYSICAL BIOLOGICAL MODELS IN ZAMFARA STATE, NIGERIA

BY

NASIRU, ZAYYANU¹ & BELLO, SHAMSUDEEN¹

¹Department of Science Education, Sokoto State University, Sokoto.

Zayyanunasiru24@gmail.com, 08034560483

Shamsudeen.bello@ssu.edu.ng, 08032890327

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17633033>

Abstract

Biology education in Nigeria faces significant challenges, including inadequate resources and a shortage of skilled educators, often limiting the use of crucial biological models for visual learning. Literature suggested that many pre-service teachers lack the requisite skills and ability to create effective models. This study investigated the effect of woodcarving and paper folding approaches on pre-service biology teachers' ability to develop biological models in Zamfara State, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design was employed. The population of the study comprises of 107 pre-service biology teachers and 84 were sampled from selected tertiary institutions. Data was collected using Biological Model Development Test (BMDT). Its reliability index of 0.89 was established through measure of internal consistency. Two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using t test and 2-way ANOVA. The study found that the woodcarving strategy significantly improved pre-service biology teachers' ability to develop biological models more than the Paper Folding Approach. Furthermore, there was a significant interaction between instructional approach and level of training, indicating the woodcarving strategy was particularly effective in enhancing ability, especially among NCE III students. Recommendations emphasize integrating practical skills like woodcarving into teacher training programs to strengthen pre-service teachers' model making abilities and enhance biology education quality.

Keywords: Woodcarving, Paper Folding, pre-service teachers, biological models, ability.

Introduction

Biology teaching is central to science education, enabling learners to understand the natural world (Tatka et al., 2023). However, in Nigeria, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited resources, and a shortage of skilled teachers hinder effective instruction (Sokoto State Ministry of Education, 2020). To enhance comprehension, teaching methods must be engaging and hands-on, with biological models serving as critical tools for illustrating complex concepts (Clark et al., 2020; Joyner & Goel, 2015). Models aid in visualizing abstract biological structures and processes, yet many Nigerian biology teachers lack the skills and confidence to construct them effectively (Yilmaz et al. 2016). The ability to design and interpret models enhances students' learning and critical

thinking (Tatka et al., 2023), but teachers often struggle due to insufficient training (Asogwa & Okanya, 2019). Comprehensive models such as wooden structures of plant cells require technical competencies like carpentry (Yilmaz et al. (2016). Incorporating woodcarving into science education fosters creativity, problem-solving, and craftsmanship (Al-husaini & Amayreh, 2021). It bridges the gap between theory and practice, improving students' retention (Menon & Azam, 2021). Historical evolution in model making from handmade wooden models in the 19th century to Styrofoam and clay models in the 20th century demonstrates its long-standing role in science teaching (Campbell, 2015; Park et al., 2019) The conventional paper approach remains popular for its accessibility and effectiveness in developing

visual and diagrammatic skills (Bailey et al., 2022). However, its limitations in durability and depth underscore the need for additional hands-on skills (Adeoye, 2020). Particularly in resource limited areas like Zamfara State, where educators adopt innovative strategies to compensate for the lack of materials (Oyovwi, 2022), integrating Woodcarving offers a practical solution. Pre-service teachers, as future science educators, must possess technical skills necessary to create accurate, engaging biological models (Hetherington & Mead, 2024). Woodcarving enhances essential competencies such as measurement, design, and spatial reasoning (Al-husaini & Amayreh, 2021). The lack of specialized training in constructing teaching aids particularly biological models during pre-service teacher education programs presents a significant barrier to effective biology instruction. As practical, hands-on learning becomes increasingly central in science education, the ability of pre-service teachers to design accurate and visually engaging models is essential for promoting student engagement and understanding of complex biological ideas. The need to enhance these practical skills among pre-service biology teachers forms the core justification for this study. In Zamfara State, pre-service teacher programs often do not include structured training in model construction, which hinders the development of essential instructional competencies. Ibrahim et al., (2019) highlight that the absence of dedicated resources and training for improvising biological models raises concerns about the preparedness of these future educators. This deficiency not only impedes their professional development and lowers their belief but also affects the overall quality of science education delivered to students in the region. Addressing this issue is crucial. By equipping pre-service teachers with specialized skills such as woodcarving they can be better prepared to create compelling, functional biological models. These skills would not only

enhance their teaching effectiveness but also promote hands-on learning, thereby elevating students' educational experiences. Empowering teachers with model making competencies ensures they can adapt to resource limited settings while still delivering engaging, student centered science instruction (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

The Skill Transfer Theory has evolved significantly since its inception in 1901 by Edward Thorndike, who proposed that learning in one situation can be transferred to another situation with similar elements. In 1988, Baldwin and Ford developed a framework for transfer of training, identifying three components: training inputs, outcomes, and conditions of transfer, which sparked a new interest in the area (Rahman, 2020). The Skill Transfer Theory provides a framework for understanding how learning in one situation can be transferred to another situation. The study on comparison of Woodcarving and Paper Folding approach on pre-service teacher's ability to develop biological models supports this theory by highlighting the importance of identifying identical elements, contextual learning, in facilitating the transfer of learning. By applying the principles of the Skill Transfer Theory, educators can design more effective learning experiences that promote the development of skills and ability.

Objectives

1. To identify the difference in ability to develop biological models between pre-service biology teachers exposed to Woodcarving and those with Paper Folding approach in Zamfara State, Nigeria.
2. To identify the difference in ability to develop biological models between NCE II and NCE III pre-service biology teachers exposed to Woodcarving and those with Paper Folding approach in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in ability to develop biological models between pre-service biology teachers exposed to Woodcarving and those exposed to Paper Folding approach in Zamafara State Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in ability to develop biological models between NCE II and NCE III pre-service biology teachers exposed to the Woodcarving and those exposed to Paper Folding approach.

Methodology

This study employed pre-test and post-test Quasi-experimental design, which is appropriate as it involves creating two groups, an experimental group receiving Woodcarving training and a control group receiving the paper Approach training. Both groups were pre-tested and post-tested on their ability to develop biological models. Following the interventions (Woodcarving training) for the experimental group, both groups will be post-tested to measure the influence of the training.

The population of this study comprises of 107 NCE II and NCE III pre-service biology teachers in the two colleges of education that enroll teacher education programs in Zamfara State which are Federal College of Education Technical, Gusau (FCET GUSAU) and College of Education, Maru (COE MARU). A sample size of 84 is chosen using Raosoft research advisor 2025. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling technique to choose NCE II and NCE III preservice biology teachers in the second and third year of their training because NCE II have not gone for teaching practice but preparing to and NCE III they have gone for teaching practice which make them to be conversant with learners and teaching aids which means they most have used one or two industrial made biological models in teaching biological concepts. Hence the need to use them in this

study and guide them on how to develop these models by themselves using Woodcarving as a skill. Thus, simple random sampling was used to choose the main participants of the study in which a numbered list of the preservice biology teachers was written on sheets of papers and placed in a contained shuffle and are picked randomly by the participants.

One research instrument, titled Biological Model Development Test (BMDT) was used to obtain data for the study. The instrument was used to evaluate a preservice biology teacher's ability to develop biological models. It was divided into five sections which are Measurement and Marking, Cutting Skills, Joining Techniques, Carving and Sculpting, and Finishing Skills. Each skill or task is rated using five points rating scale on 1= Needs Improvement, 2= Developing, 3= Competent, Proficient and 5= Excellent. The instrument assesses accuracy, tool use, and technique proficiency, providing a comprehensive view of the individual's abilities. Additionally, space is provided for comments and an overall assessment, including total score and competency level.

To ensure the validity of the instrument four experts were involved, three of which are from the department of science education Sokoto State University and one from the Woodcarving and joinery department Government Technical College (GTC) Farfaru Sokoto State. A draft copy of the instrument was served to them for face, content and criterion validity. Their feedbacks are used to calculate the Content Validity Index (CVI) using: $CVI = \frac{\text{Total items agreed by all expert assessable}}{\text{Total items judged}}$. The validity

index for the instrument is greater than the standard index required for any instrument to be valid for academic research, the CVI obtained for the Woodcarving and Paper Folding Approach Biological Model Development Test (BDMT) is 0.78. Furthermore, to ensure that the instrument

is reliable a pilot study was conducted to a non-sampled institution within the population and administered to 20 education biology preservice teachers. Their responses were put into SPSS software to compute the Crombach's alpha value of the instrument which is 0.89.

The method of data collection was a general introduction to the management of the selected institutions. The researcher with the help of two trained assistants started by assessing student ability while developing models before the training which served as pre-test by using Biological Model Development Test (BDMT) then the experimental was trained on how to make physical biological models such as plant cell and animal cell using woodcarving approach while control groups were trained using paper approach. The training lasted for six weeks. Lastly, the Biological Model Development Test

was used during the training session for the second time as a Pos-test.

The method of data analysis used to test the null hypotheses, one was Independent Samples t-test while Two-way ANOVA was used to test null hypothesis two. T-test was selected to compare the mean of two independent groups (Experimental and Control group), while two-way ANOVA was used to compare the mean of two independent groups with each having two categories of students (NCE II and NCE III). For Instant, BMDT scores of NCE II and NCE III students in the experimental group was compared with the BMDT scores of NCE II and NCE III students in the control group to examine the main effect of each instructional intervention on each level of NCE students used in the study. All the analyses were conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Figure: one and two show samples of activities for experimental and control groups.

Figure 1 Sample of Activity in Experimental Group

Figure 2 Sample of Activity in Control Group

Results

Null hypothesis

H₀1: There is no significant difference in ability to develop biological model between pre-service biology teachers exposed to woodwork and those exposed to paper folding approach in Zamafara State Nigeria.

Table 1: Independent Samples t-test for difference in ability between pre-service teachers exposed to woodwork and those exposed to the paper Folding approach

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Woodwork	47	57.44	6.01	82	5.51	.000	Rejected
Paper Folding Practice	37	49.06	7.05				

Source: field work 2025

$\alpha=0.05$

The results in Table 1 shows statistical analysis that compares the ability to develop biological models between two groups: those exposed to woodwork and those exposed to the paper folding approach.

The analysis reveals a significant difference in the ability to develop biological models between the two groups, with a t-value of 5.51, a p-value

of .000, and a degree of freedom of 82, indicating a statistically significant difference. However, the statistical results, contradicted the null hypothesis two stating that there is no significant difference in the ability to develop biological models between the two groups. With this the null hypothesis one is hereby rejected.

H₀2: There is no significant difference in ability between NCE II and NCE III pre-service biology teacher’s exposed to wood work and those exposed to paper folding approach on development of biological models in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Two-Way ANOVA Results for Ability to Develop Biological Models

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Instructional Approach (A)	2178.889	2	2178.889	48.899	.000
Level of Training (B)	2415.556	2	2415.556	54.251	.000
A x B Interaction	264.778	4	264.778	5.939	.016
Error	4945.556	75	44.758		
Total	438904.222	83			

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Corrected Total	10804.667	84			

Source: field work 2025

$\alpha=0.05$

The results in Table 2 indicate significant main effect for Instructional Approach ($F(1, 84) = 48.899, p < 0.000$), and a significant difference in ability to develop biological models between pre-service biology teachers exposed to the woodwork and those exposed to the paper folding practice. significant main effect for Level of Training ($F(1, 84) = 54.251, p < 0.000$), suggesting a significant difference in ability to develop biological models between NCE II and NCE III pre-service biology teachers, and

significant interaction between Instructional Approach and Level of Training ($F(1, 84) = 5.939, p = 0.016$), indicating that the effect of Instructional Approach on ability to develop biological models differs significantly between NCE II and NCE III pre-service biology teachers.

To further examine the significant interaction, a Tukey's HSD post-hoc test was conducted. The results of the Tukey's HSD for Ability to Develop Biological Models are presented in Table 4 below:

Table 3: Results of the Tukey's HSD Results for Ability to Develop Biological Models

(I) Instructional Approach / Level of Training	(J) Instructional Approach / Level of Training	M Diff (I-J)	SE	P	95% CI
Woodcarving/ NCE II	Paper Folding approach/ NCE II	6.99	1.43	.000	4.14, 9.84
Woodcarving/ NCE II	Woodcarving/ NCE III	-12.08	1.53	.000	-15.12, -9.04
Woodcarving/ NCE II	Paper Folding approach/ NCE III	2.73	1.55	.201	-0.35, 5.81
Woodcarving / NCE III	Paper Folding approach/ NCE II	19.07	1.53	.000	16.03, 22.11
Woodcarving/ NCE III	Paper Folding approach/ NCE III	14.81	1.59	.000	11.65, 17.97
Paper Folding approach/ NCE II	Paper Folding approach / NCE III	-4.27	1.44	.016	-7.13, -1.41

Source: field work 2025

$\alpha=0.05$

The result of Tukey's HSD in Table 3 indicate: Significant differences in ability to develop biological models between the following groups: Woodcarving / NCE II and Paper Folding approach/ NCE II (M Diff = 6.99, $p = .000$), Woodcarving/ NCE II and Woodcarving / NCE III (M Diff = -12.08, $p = .000$), Woodcarving / NCE II and Paper Folding approach/ NCE III (M

Diff = 2.73, $p = .201$), Woodcarving/ NCE III and Paper Folding approach/ NCE II (M Diff = 19.07, $p = .000$), Woodcarving / NCE III and Paper Folding approach/ NCE III (M Diff = 14.81, $p = .000$), Paper Folding approach/ NCE II and Paper Folding approach/ NCE III (M Diff = -4.27, $p = .016$)

Therefore, the null hypothesis, which stated that "there is no significant difference in ability to

develop biological models between NCE II and NCE III pre-service biology teachers exposed to the Woodcarving and those exposed to paper folding approach”, is rejected. The results suggest that the Woodcarving instructional approach is more effective in enhancing ability among pre-service biology teachers, particularly among NCE III students.

Discussion of the findings

The findings of hypothesis one showed a significant difference in the ability to develop biological models between pre-service biology teachers who were exposed to the Woodcarving and those who used the paper folding approach. This support finding from previous studies, such as Adeoye et al. (2022), which emphasize the importance of tactile learning experiences in grasping complex scientific concepts. Furthermore, the Woodcarving approach provides an opportunity for pre-service teachers to experiment and engage in iterative learning. The transformative potential of hands on methodologies aligns with the research of Abdon-Liwanag (2023), which found that 3D modeling experiences significantly boosted students' comprehension and retention of biological concepts. This contrast, Harun et al. (2019), there is often a disconnect between theoretical knowledge and the application of that knowledge in teaching practices when practical experiences are lacking.

The findings from hypothesis two reveal a statistically significant interaction between instructional approach and level of training in relation to the ability of pre-service biology teachers to develop biological models. This interaction suggests that the effectiveness of a teaching method in developing modeling skills is not the same across academic levels. Specifically, the Woodcarving approach proved to be particularly effective for students at the NCE III level, whose ability to design and construct biological models was significantly

higher than that of their peers trained with the paper folding approach. This indicates that the Woodcarving method, embedded in experiential and hands-on learning, becomes increasingly beneficial as students' progress in their training and are more cognitively and practically prepared to engage in complex tasks. This outcome is supported by the work of Abdon-Liwanag (2023), who emphasized that experiential learning approaches such as carpentry do not only enhance conceptual understanding but also promote the practical application of knowledge. Engaging in the manipulation of materials and the construction of three-dimensional models encourages learners to interact actively with abstract biological concepts. This active involvement fosters a deeper level of comprehension and retention and equips pre-service biology teachers with valuable skills needed for classroom instruction. When learners build models themselves, they are compelled to think critically about biological structures and processes, translating theoretical knowledge into physical representations. This process cultivates both mastery and confidence in teaching content that often poses challenges in secondary science classrooms. In contrast, the findings indicate that the paper folding approach may not sufficiently support the development of practical modeling skills, especially among more advanced students such as those in NCE III. As students progress in their training, they typically require instructional strategies that are more dynamic, engaging, and reflective of real world teaching demands. The paper based approach, which relies heavily on passive visual representation, may fall short in providing the level of interaction and skill application needed at this stage. This concern is in line with the findings of Yıldız and Emre ÜrünArıcı (2021), who highlighted that limiting instruction to traditional, non-interactive methods, can hinder the development of functional teaching competencies, particularly for learners nearing

professional readiness. The implications of this finding are significant for both the teaching of biology and the preparation of future educators. For biology education, the result suggests that incorporating hands-on modeling approaches like Woodcarving can greatly improve the capacity of future teachers to develop and utilize instructional models effectively. These skills are essential in making abstract biological content more accessible and engaging for secondary school learners. For teacher education programs, by embedding experiential model building activities into the curriculum, colleges of education can better equip pre-service teachers with the competence and confidence required to teach biology effectively through visual, demonstrative, and engaging means.

Conclusion

The findings of this study conclude that the woodcarving instructional approach is more effective in enhancing the ability of pre-service biology teachers in Zamfara State, Nigeria, to develop biological models. The results indicate that hands-on activities and applied learning experiences significantly improve learners' ability and overall performance. Furthermore, the level of study of preservice biology teachers influences their ability to construct biological models, drawing attention to the importance of considering training level in instructional design.

Recommendation

1. Educational policy makers are encouraged to promote the inclusion of practical, hands-on activities and applied learning methods within teacher education programmes.
2. Lecturers in tertiary institutions should integrate experiential activities, such as woodcarving, into their curriculum to strengthen pre-service biology teachers' ability to construct biological models.
3. Tertiary institutions should take into account the training levels of pre-service biology

teachers by ensuring the provision of appropriate resources and materials for each stage of the teacher education programme.

Reference

- Abdon-Liwanag, B. (2023). The Influence of 3-D Model Biological Systems in Understanding Cellular Diversity. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 4(4), 85–95. <https://doi.org/10.54476/ioer-imrj/009169>
- Adeoye, G. A. (2020). Effects Of Modelling Clay and Demonstration Kit On Senior School Students' Performance in Cell Division in Omu-Aran, Nigeria. *University Of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria*.
- Al-husaini, A. S. A., & Amayreh, E. A. (2021). The Effectiveness of a Strategy Based on the Concepts of a Growth Mindset for Teaching Carpentry and Decoration in Developing Practical Vocational Skills and Imaginative Thinking. *Canadian Center of Science and Education*, 17(4), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v17n4p1>
- Asogwa, A., & Okanya, A. (2019). Skill Improvement Needs of Teachers of Carpentry and Joinery in Technical Colleges in Enugu State. *Industrial Technical Education Journal*, 1(1), 253–259.
- Bailey, R., Kim, D., Bochenko, M. J., Yang, C., Dees, D. C., & Jung, J. (2022). The use of clay modeling to increase high school biology vocabulary learning. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching and Learning*, 15(2), 232–244. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIT-07-2021-0053>
- Campbell, T. (2015). Model-based science teaching and learning. 87(4), 8–11. https://doi.org/10.2505/4/tst19_087_04_8
- Clark, C. A. C., Helikar, T., & Dauer, J. (2020). Simulating a computational biological model, rather than reading, elicits changes

- in brain activity during biological reasoning. *CBE Life Sciences Education*, 19(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.19-11-0237>
- Harun, I. Y., Made Putrawan, I., & Miarsyah, M. (2019). Biological teachers' motivation based on personality and self efficacy. *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 6(6), 92–100. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3266120>
- Hetherington, L., & Mead, S. (2024). Models and modelling in science teaching. *Learning to Teach Science in the Secondary School*, 142–154. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003110187-12>
- Ibrahim, S. A., Ibrahim, A., Ya, S., & Abdullahi, S. A. (2019). Improvisation in Teaching and Learning Biology in Senior Secondary Schools: Prospects and Challenges. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Multidisciplinary Studies*, 5(11), 33–36.
- Joyner, D. A., & Goel, A. K. (2015). Improving inquiry-driven modeling in science education through interaction with intelligent tutoring agents. *International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces, Proceedings IUI, 2015-January* (March 2015), 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2678025.2701398>
- Menon, D., & Azam, S. (2021). Investigating Preservice Teachers' Science Teaching Self-Efficacy: An Analysis of Reflective Practices. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 19(8), 1587–1607. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-020-10131-4>
- Oyovwi, E. O. (2022). Biology Education in Nigeria : Issues and Challenges in the 21st Century. *Journal of the Faculty of Education, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria*, 12(July), 1–9.
- Park, B.-Y., Rodriguez, L., & Campbell, T. (2019). Commentary: Using Models to Teach Science. *The Science Teacher*, 87(4), 8–11. https://doi.org/10.2505/4/tst19_087_04_8
- Rahman, A. A. (2020). Tracing the Evolution of Transfer of Training: A Review Article. *Annals of Social Sciences & Management Studies*, 5(4). <https://doi.org/10.19080/asm.2020.05.555668>
- Sokoto State Ministry of Education. (2020). Annual education performance report: Challenges and strategies in science education. *Sokoto State Government Press*.
- Tatka, L. T., Smith, L. P., Hellerstein, J. L., & Sauro, H. M. (2023). Adapting modeling and simulation credibility standards to computational systems biology. *Journal of Translational Medicine*, 5, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12967-023-04290-5>
- Yıldız, EmreÜrünArıcı, N. (2021). Yıldız, E. &ÜrünArıcı, N. (2021). An investigation of pre-service Science teachers' self-efficacy beliefs towards teaching and their teaching skills. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 8(2), 588-603. AN, 8.
- Yilmaz, M., Güneş, P., & Katircioğlu, H. T. (2016). Examination of the teacher self-efficacy of pre-service biology and science teachers in terms of different variables. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 13(1), 45–54. <https://doi.org/10.12973/tused.10156a>